

NUTRI•KNOW

STRUVITE (IT)

GAS LOOP (IT)

RENURE (BE)

SOS_AQUAE
(IT)

POCKETBOER 2
(BE)

FERTICOOP-GO
(ES)

Grass2Algae
(BE)

Manure
Management
Tool (ES)

MOPS (IE)

Slurry
Concentrator
(ES)

Duncannon Blue
Flag Farming (IE)

Biorefinery
Glas (IE)

Exchanging easy-to-understand nutrient management knowledge with farmers

NUTRI-KNOW aims to improve nutrient management practices in agriculture by establishing an ongoing cycle of knowledge exchange for the benefit of both farmers and the environment.

SOS_AQUAE

Microfiltered Digestate treatment to Fertilization: an economic sustainable solution

SOS_AQUAE aims to advance and promote sustainable agricultural techniques associated with the use of "renewable" fertilisers derived from slurry and digestate treatment. The goal is to enhance the efficient use of existing nutrients on farms while reducing reliance on synthetic mineral fertilisers.

Economic assessment

An assessment of irrigation and fertilization costs and incomes from the maize production has been performed comparing innovative digested microfiltration followed by drip lines fertilization technology (MFT+SDI) with the Business As Usual (raw digestate + urea + sprinkler irrigation). Results suggest a balancing per hectare farmed using the innovative method MFT+SDI.

	MFT+SDI	BAU	Delta
Irrigation €	835	495	340
S/L separation + microfiltration €	100	0	100
Digestate transport and distribution €	120	120	0
Urea €	0	170	-170
Total Costs (€/ha)	1,055	785	270
Maiz yield (t/ha 33% d.m.)	68	60	8
€/ton of maize	45	45	0
Total Incomes (€/ha)	3,060	2,700	360
Profit (€/ha)	2,005	1,915	90

Conclusion

The results obtained highlight that fertirrigation with microfiltered digestate in the drip lines besides being both technically feasible and economically and environmentally sustainable, allow high productivity by reducing external inputs, and it is proposed as one of the most efficient and sustainable practices in the digestate management scenario.

Drip lines specially designed to prevent clogging and fouling

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